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Table of Contents

0. Executive Summary 2

1. PP-internal part (April 1, 9:00- April 2, 11:00) 3

 1.1 Agenda 3

 1.2 Participants 5

 1.3. Main outcomes 7

 1.4 Online resources 11

2. LP-JS meeting (April 2, 12:00- 13:30) 12

 2.1 Agenda 12

 2.2 Participants 12

 2.3. Main outcomes 13

Conclusions 13

0. Executive Summary

The second GUTTA Steering Committee (SC) meeting has taken place, as planned during M16 of the project lifetime (i.e. April 2020). However, due to emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, it has been transformed into a web conference.

The SC meeting consisted of three plenary sessions among Partners and a group call among the project coordination unit of the LP and the GUTTA Project Officer at the JS. All events took place from April 1 to 2, 2020.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at <https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>.

1. PP-internal part (April 1, 9:00- April 2, 11:00)

The event is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes, and online published contents.

1.1 Agenda

8:45	Access to the videoconference tool
Session A	Recap on work done
	<i>Scope of each talk in this session will be to share with the PPs the technical progress since SCm1. Short questions will be taken after each talk. A group discussion will close the session.</i>
9:00	Welcome and overview of SCm2 <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
9:15	Advancements with VISIR-2 <i>Lorenzo Carelli (CMCC)</i>
9:45	Objective assessment of a new Italy-Croatia route <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
10:15	Group Screenshot
10:20	Balcony break
10:45	Results from UniZd simulator and their analysis <i>Josip Orović (UniZd) and Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
11:15	THETIS-MRV: Adriatic sea ferries and feedback from user experience <i>Maria Mihalić (CSA)</i>
11:45	Group discussion
12:30	Fitness and self-cooked lunch break

Session B	Our mission
	<i>Scope of this session is to review the technical work to be done in the remainder of 2020 and, in some cases, beyond. It is organized by PPs and Deliverables they are in charge of</i>
14:30	D4.3.1 Report on administrative requirements for new Italy-Croatia maritime routes <i>Lia Piteni (AdSP)</i>

15:00	D4.2.2 Report on training of MRV Inspection personnel D4.3.1 Report on administrative requirements for new Italy-Croatia maritime routes <i>(MMPI delegated Sandro Vidas of CSA to report them the outcome of SCm2 discussion on these topics)</i>
15:30	D4.2.1 Guidance document on implementation of Monitoring and Reporting of MRV D5.1.1 Report on MRV life-cycle implementation potential and issues <i>Maria Mihalić (CSA)</i>
16:00	Stretching break
16:15	D5.1.3 Report on validation of vessel CO2 emission model D2.2.7 Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed journal paper <i>Josip Orović (UniZd)</i>
16:45	D4.1.2 Report on VISIR software advancements <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
17:15	D1.2.6 Project-internal CO2 emissions report <i>Amal Salhi (CMCC)</i>
17:45	Discussion <i>all PP</i>

Session C	Next steps
	<i>Scope of this session is to recap on the various aspects of project implementation (Communication, Finance, Technical aspects) and discuss amendments.</i>
9:00	Communication Recap <i>Laura Caciagli (CMCC)</i>
9:30	Technical Recap <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
10:00	Financial Recap <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
10:30	Balcony break
11:00	Any other business

1.2 Participants

On day 1, 13 people took part to the webex, as documented in both Tab.1 and Fig.1.

Table 1 List of participants of day 1's participants

Figure 1 Group screenshot of day 1's participants to the PP-internal part of SCm2.

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
2	Amal	Sahli	CMCC
3	Gordana	Vukelić-Čemeljić	CSA
4	Josip	Orović	UniZd
5	Laura	Caciagli	CMCC
6	Lorenzo	Carelli	CMCC
7	Evangelia	Piteni	AdSP
8	Maria	Mihalić	CSA
9	Martin	Zrilić	UniZd
10	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
11	Sabina	Rako Juravic	Unizd
12	Sandro	Vidas	CSA
13	Zoran	Pavin	UniZd

On day 2, 16 people took part to the webex, as documented in both Tab.2 and Fig.2.

Figure 2 Group screenshot of day 2's participants to the PP-internal part of SCm2.

Table 2 List of participants of day 1's participants to the PP-internal part of SCm2

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
2	Amal	Sahli	CMCC
3	Gordana	Vukelić-Čemeljić	CSA
4	Josip	Orović	UniZd
5	Laura	Caciagli	CMCC
6	Lorenzo	Carelli	CMCC
7	Evangelia	Piteni	AdSP
8	Maria	Mihalić	CSA
9	Martin	Zrilić	UniZd
10	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
11	Sabina	Rako Juravic	Unizd
12	Sandro	Vidas	CSA
13	Zoran	Pavin	UniZd
14	Rita	Lecci	CMCC
15	Matteo	Scuro	CMCC
16	Francesco	Palermo	CMCC

1.3. Main outcomes

Agostini

She introduced and chaired the virtual meeting, stating that it represents the turning point of the GUTTA project, as 15 out of 30 of the foreseen project months are now elapsed.

Furthermore, she presented figures about financial absorption per WP and budget lines. These data point to an overall underspending of the project (cumulative absorption of both RP1 and RP2 was about 73% of planned resources). The underspending is mainly due to two Project Partners (MMPI and AdSP) not reporting any expenses so far. Furthermore, the LP took direct responsibilities for two deliverables (D. 2.1.3 and D. 3.1.2) for which those PPs were in charge. Corresponding effort should be reimbursed via a minor budget amendment. It amounts to about 19 kEUR that should be transferred to the LP.

Mannarini

He presented the work done by LP on D. 3.1.2 for developing and applying a method for an objective assessment of a new CB route. The methodology is based on a Pareto-efficiency analysis in the space of route duration and CO2 emissions. It has been applied to the Bari-Zadar route, comparing 4 alternative itineraries, including a direct maritime link, so far not existing. It can be replicated on other routes, comparing the efficiency of various combinations of both terrestrial vehicles and ferry boats. However, the limits of this approach are also discussed: traffic flow data were not used (only some CIMIS data were available and for just the Croatian harbours) and they could greatly affect the final outcome of the analysis.

Furthermore, he also illustrated the work done by LP in the frame of D.3.2.2, jointly with UniZd. The data collected from the bridge simulator allowed for reconstruction of the speed loss in waves of a specific Ro-Pax vessel. The LP developed a numerical framework for fitting a multi-dimensional model based on elementary functions and assessed its quality. The identified fit parameters will be used within the VISIR-2 model for the GUTTA tool for computation of eco-routes.

He also proposed a roadmap for the finalization of the new VISIR-2 features and its pre-operational developments. Transition to operation is forecast by EOY.

Finally, he presented some results from a manuscript on analysis of Ro-Pax emission data obtained from THETIS-MRV and processed by CMCC authors that is being submitted for an International conference on maritime big data¹.

Caciagli

As Communication Officer of the LP, she reviewed the communication activities carried out by the GUTTA Consortium.

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/mbdw2020/mbdw-home>

Two physical events were organized in 2019: the KOM and the first SC meeting (SCm1). Furthermore, GUTTA was presented at several conferences and meetings, both in Italy and Croatia, and presence on the social channels was initiated (mainly on Twitter and LinkedIn). Several target groups were already addressed, including a group of high school students who attended the KOM (D. 1.1.1). Internal communication is up and running, with several mailing lists in place and instant messaging among PPs already working. A dissemination mailing list, capitalizing on contacts of the stakeholders' database (D. 2.1.3) is maintained by the LP and has been used for disseminating online the project brochures (D. 2.2.1). Furthermore, in 2019 GUTTA contributed to the EC-day in Croatia (see 1.3.1). For the next project months, also in view of restrictions to people mobility due to the ongoing pandemic, GUTTA aims to make use of webinars for disseminating its outcomes. These can benefit from a dedicated protocol already in use at the LP.

Orović

He presented the work done by UniZd in installing and operating the bridge simulator, partly supported by GUTTA funds. In agreement with LP, the simulator has been driven by specific combinations of meteo-marine fields chosen in order to optimally sample the response of the vessel. Data collected were then analyzed by LP. The same methodology will be used for modeling the CO₂ emissions (D. 4.1.1). However, the bridge simulator will first have to be coupled to the engine simulator, also available at the UniZd facilities.

Furthermore, he reviewed the plan for the next deliverables, including a joint publication with LP (D. 2.2.7) and validation of simulated results vs. experimental data collected on board dedicated cruises carried out by UniZd in the past few months (D. 3.1.3, D. 5.1.3).

Vidas

In reference to GUTTA project SO3, he mentioned that the Croatian shipowners are presently mostly interested in a Ro-Pax route calling at Šibenik. Also, incoming freight flow from non-EU Countries should be facilitated. For instance, Durrës (Albania), would be an interesting port to be involved. Given the availability of AdSP to use of Barletta harbour for Ro-Pax vessels (see Piteni below), a new round trip route: Šibenik- Durrës – Barletta – Šibenik has been proposed, see Fig.3. This is yet a new proposal with respect to the outcome of SCm1(cf. Fig 4 in D. 1.3.1.). However, there is a continuity in supporting a route involving a third Country with respect to both Italy and Croatia and in the fact that a round-trip route is preferred to a stick.

Figure 3 Hypothesis of a new CB round trip route involving both Italy, Croatia, and Albania. Blue legs: existing routes; Red legs: new route.

Vidas was also delegated by MMPI to speak for them at SCm2. In this respect, he represented to GUTTA PPs the temporary difficulty of the Ministry of the Sea, Transport, and Infrastructure to deploy staff to the project, given the ongoing issues related to the COVID-19 pandemic and also the Croatian Presidency of the Council of the European Union². The latter is totally overlapping with GUTTA’s RP3 (January 1- June 30, 2020).

About the deliverable on administrative requirements on the new CB route (D. 4.3.1), he stressed the fact that, unless the passenger flow exceeds 300 000 people/year, neither the State Administration nor the Agency for Coastal Maritime Traffic³ are in a position of making a public

² <https://eu2020.hr/>

³ <https://agencija-zolpp.hr/>

expression of interest for a new route. Instead, the initiative must come from a private ship operator.

Vidas said to be confident that the training of EU-MRV inspection personnel (D. 4.2.2) will be fulfilled by MMPI, maybe with some delay. Instead, he suggested that MMPI might be interested in a budget amendment, in order to open a tender for purchasing some equipment.

Piteni

She informed the GUTTA consortium that the slowing down related to the change of management at AdSP is slowly being recovered. In particular, a procedure for the selection of the FLC has recently been concluded. It is presently awaiting for a signature by the AdSP President and should then be published by the end of the week. Furthermore, the procedure for the selection of a technical assistance for GUTTA will be completed within the next 10 days.

With respect to the new routes, she stated that:

- The decision about the new route should involve a table of local stakeholders, to be organized by AdSP
- Data-based evidence should be aimed to and, in this respect, she pointed to the official statistics of passenger and freight flows at the ports of Bari and Barletta⁴
- She will check if there is any similar study already performed by AdSP in the past
- The analysis performed by LP in the frame of D. 3.1.2 could be repeated for other couples of ports in the Adriatic
- AdSP preference is for using the port of Barletta, were ship draughts up to 7 m are allowed. Also, Barletta does not suffer from the congestion issues of the Bari port.

Mihalić

She reported about CSA activity on both D. 3.1.1 and D. 3.2.1. In latter deliverable, not only the EU-MRV is compared to the IMO DCS and to the China DC, but also feedback of some Croatian stakeholders on the THETIS-MRV system is collected.

In reference to next deliverables D. 4.2.1 and D. 5.1.1, the objectives stated in GUTTA AF are now obsolete, as the EU-MRV is already in place and the first reporting period has been completed last year. Furthermore, CSA assessed that there is no availability by the shipowners to distribute per-voyage basis CO₂ emission data, not even for the sake of development of the eco-routes tool. Therefore, Mannarini recommended to rather focus on the ongoing debate on the alignment of EU-MRV to IMO-DCS, keeping into account both the EC proposal of February 2019, the stakeholders' consultation process, the new proposal by the European Parliament of January 2020, and its forthcoming discussion (planned for June 2020).

CSA points out that the ECSA's opinion is as follows:

⁴ <https://www.adspmam.it/i-porti/statistiche/>

1. MRV to IMO DCS: The EU MRV Regulation should be fully aligned now with the IMO Fuel Data Collection System. Also, alignment with IMO fuel data collection system could only happen following an amendment of the Regulation through the EU Parliament and the Council.
2. CO₂: Supporting the ambitious international framework in the IMO, set by the initial strategy for the reduction of GHG emissions from ships, agreed by MEPC 72.

Carelli

He presented the technical developments of VISIR-2 model. They regard recoding into python, enhancement of computational performance, validation with respect to both VISIR-1 and analytical benchmarks, new visualization features, and first examples of multi-objective optimization.

The work refers to already submitted deliverables D. 3.1.4, D. 3.2.3 and will be continued in the frame of D. 4.1.2, D. 4.4.1, D. 5.1.4.

Salhi

She presented an analysis of the voyage reports collected so far, to be used for the assessment of the project-internal CO₂ emissions (D.1.2.6).

In total, 17 reports were analyzed, including those referring to preparatory meetings of the GUTTA proposal (in 2016 and 2017). CO₂ emissions, travelled distance, and emissions intensity were computed. The results were plotted with respect to both time and the PP the traveler belongs to. Guests of the KOM and the Advisory Board member (Mr. Madeira of EMSA) were included. It is seen the prominent role in terms of CO₂ emissions played by the GUTTA KOM and its SCm1 (see Fig.4).

Finally, some emissions offsetting modalities were presented, including contribution to reforestation, clean water supply and provision of biomass cookstoves in developing Countries, funding of small power plants using renewable energy.

1.4 Online resources

Presentations of SCm2 can be found at the following URL:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1iBwPDDL7I4LZLWuw_xE7nBQJhfj58KB

Figure 4 CO2 emissions due to GUTTA meetings to date, with each column referring to the journey of a single traveller, and column color referring to the CO2 intensity (emissions per unit distance).

2. LP-JS meeting (April 2, 12:00- 13:30)

The event is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes.

2.1 Agenda

Session D	LP-JS skype call
	<i>Scope of this session is to recap and discuss amendments. In presence of the project officer of GUTTA at the IT-HR Joint-Secretariat</i>
12:00-13:30	Technical recap and discussion of criticalities (IT-HR JS and CMCC)

2.2 Participants

On day 2, four people took part to the skype video call, as documented in both Tab.3.

Table 3 List of participants to the skype video call between the LP and the JS.

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Paolo	Rotoni	Interreg V A Italy - Croatia 2014-2020 Joint Secretariat
2	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
3	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
4	Laura	Caciagli	CMCC

2.3. Main outcomes

Mannarini

He recapitulated the main technical achievements of GUTTA to date, emphasizing the level of joint development among PPs, describing the potential contribution of the project outcomes to mitigate the carbon intensity of maritime transport in the Adriatic region and the analysis of Ro-Pax emission data done in the paper for the MBDW2020 conference.

Agostini

She mentioned the financial issues related to underspending.

Rotoni

He appreciated the advancements of GUTTA consortium, backed the proposal to update some obsolete points of the AF relative to the actions in support of EU-MRV, but pointed out the necessity to achieve a deeper involvement of the two public partners (MMPI and AdSP), also with respect to financial reporting.

Conclusions

GUTTA SCm2 was a productive event with a quite good participation from both project partners and the Project Officer at the Italy-Croatia Joint Secretariat through a virtual meeting tool.

The meeting set a turning point in the story of the project that now has produced most of the preparatory material needed for its future developments. Criticalities were addressed with a constructive criticism. Next SC meeting (SCm3) is provisionally planned for the first half of November 2020, in Zadar.

With respect to the horizontal aspects of Communication and the three project Specific Objectives, the situation and next steps to be done can be summarized as follows:

Communication

It is recommended to review information of the presence of all PPs on all social channels, in order to amplify the messages from the GUTTA consortium. The communication officer (Caciagli) will collect these data from the PPs and will ensure that the communication flow is harmonized and coherent.

Furthermore, it is of paramount importance that the communication activities by individual PPs are aligned with both the IT-HR Interreg guidelines (Factsheet n. 8⁵) and the GUTTA Communication Strategy (D. 2.1.3). PPs should refrain from initiatives not compliant with these principles, since they may weaken the effectiveness of the project communication plan.

SO1

VISIR-2 coding proceeds well (validation, performance enhancement, new technical features added). There is some delay due to additional and unexpected tasks performed by LP. A Successful integration of UniZd results into LP work for the eco-tool has been performed in RP2. In SCm2 a roadmap to deliver an operational service for eco-routes has been outlined and the first operational prototype could be available by end of 2020. Therefore, the GUTTA consortium should be able to deliver its contribution to the 4.1O1 Output Indicator “Improved multimodal transport services” of the IT-HR Interreg Programme.

SO2

This specific objective is now outdated. In fact, given the delayed start of the IT-HR Standard projects, it refers to an EU-MRV phase that was completed already during GUTTA RP1 (June 30, 2019). Furthermore, no per-voyage basis data will be provided by shipowners. However, the delay in start date allowed GUTTA to provide an analysis of THETIS-MRV data and a conference paper documenting it was prepared. SCm2 suggested to follow the developments in the regulatory environment (EU Commission and EU Parliament proposals for MRV amendment) and disseminate information about the process.

SO3

A public expression of interest for a new route seems not to be feasible, neither in Italy nor Croatia. Instead, a private initiative (shipowners) should then be approved by the public authorities. SCm2 conclusion is that CSA and AdSP liaise more tightly for listening to the needs of the territorial stakeholders. An option is also to replicate the objective assessment made in D. 3.1.2 for other CB routes. Also, this assessment could be integrated with passenger and freight flow data and AdSP should verify if studies of these type were already performed by its technical department.

⁵ https://www.italy-croatia.eu/documents/20126/87333/03-20180719_Factsheet_8_Communication.pdf/85ba26b6-9274-a11f-3ccd-1396be4f216d?t=1548328813954